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DETECTING WATER QUALITY RESPONSES TO LAND MANAGEMENT CHANGES AT THE WATERSHED SCALE: WHY IS IT SO DIFFICULT?

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ABSTRACT

Conducting successful research to relate land use practices to water quality at the watershed scale is difficult for many reasons, including lack of control of many aspects of the land use, time lags in watershed and water quality response to changes, and reluctance of funding agencies to fully implement the most powerful research design, the before-after paired-watershed design. Detecting water quality responses to changes in land management programs, which can be considered applied watershed-scale research experiments, is even more difficult. When adequate data are available, however, it is possible to document the success of land management programs, and to build the case that observed changes are responses to management actions, not coincidental changes due to other factors such as weather.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, government agencies that fund watershed-scale water quality research and demonstration projects have been under intense pressure from Congress and the General Accounting Office to demonstrate that implementation of land management practices, so-called Best Management Practices or BMPs, actually leads to improvements in water quality. U.S. EPA's Clean Water Act Section 319 programs, including the National Monitoring Programs, were threatened with elimination in the late 1990s (Charles Sutfin, oral presentation at U.S. EPA National Monitoring Program Workshop, Breckenridge, CO, Sept. 12, 2002). More recently, several USDA programs have faced a similar threat (Todd Brace, USDA Farm Service Agency, oral presentation at Sandusky River Symposium, Tiffin, Ohio, June 28, 2006).

The success of BMPs in improving water quality has frequently been demonstrated at the plot or field scale, but it is often claimed that no one has ever documented such results at the watershed scale. While this is something of an exaggeration, such studies are often not successful, even when well-planned and well-implemented. This paper presents a comparison of field research at varying

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scales, which suggests why successful research at the watershed scale is so challenging. We also present as a case study the Lake Erie Conservation Reserve Enhancement Program (CREP) in Ohio, for which water quality assessments are being provided by Heidelberg College's National Center for Water Quality Research (NCWQR). Land management programs are essentially large scale exercises in applied field research, and demonstrating their success involves the same challenges as are encountered in watershed-scale research, plus perhaps a few more.

FIELD RESEARCH AT VARYING SCALES

It is useful to begin by considering the desirable attributes of a field research plan. These include the following:

- Manipulating as opposed to observing
- Being in control of all aspects of the experiment
- Avoiding extraneous influences
- Applying various levels of treatment
- Having a control (no treatment)
- Replicating the experiment to assure consistent response

Plot Scale Research

At the plot scale, the desirable attributes are generally all achieved or achievable. Plot studies generally involved direct manipulation of one or a few environmental variables to determine how they affect the characteristic of interest. The researcher or his institution generally owns the land on which the experiment is carried out. Careful choice and/or preparation of the location leads to uniform slopes and soil properties throughout the set of plots. Rainfall simulators are often used to assure that each plot receives the same amount of water uniformly over its entire extent. Several levels of treatment are generally applied, and treatments are generally replicated. Well established experimental designs minimize bias from unrecognized environmental gradients or other inhomogeneities within the study area.

Field Scale Research

At the field scale, the desirable attributes are more difficult to achieve. The basic experiment is still typically carried out by manipulation, usually of one environmental variable. The researcher or his institution generally owns or controls the land on which the experiment is carried out. Homogeneous slopes and soil properties are much less likely, however. Rainfall is likely to be provided by Nature, is likely to vary in intensity and amount from place to place in the study area, and the researcher does not control the timing of its arrival or its intensity. Thus the researcher is becoming a passive observer, rather than an active manipulator, of some important aspects of the experiment. The experiment

is likely to have fewer levels of treatment (often only one) than would be true of a plot study, and while a control field is likely to be part of the experimental design, replication competes with levels of treatment for research dollars.

Inferring Cause and Effect

One of the major reasons that the attributes listed above are desirable is that they are important in separating cause and effect relationships from coincidental occurrences. If we observe two things A and B happening, we may suspect that one caused the other, but we can't always be sure which one caused the other, and we must acknowledge that it is possible that no causality exists. But if we actively do A and B happens immediately thereafter (manipulation), and if B happens every time we do A (replication), and if B does not happen if we do not do A (control), and if the degree of B is somehow related to the degree of A (levels of treatment), then we have strong confidence that doing A causes B.

As the scale of a field experiment increases, it becomes necessary to include fewer and fewer of these desirable attributes, and confident inference of cause and effect becomes more elusive. At the field and watershed scales, the experimental design called the paired-field (or paired-watershed) design is the best approach to assuring that observed responses are due to the manipulation and not to chance, random weather effects, differences in field properties, etc. "Paired" implies two, and usually there are just two fields, but the approach can be used with more than two if resources permit. The fields (or watersheds) should be as close together as possible and as similar as possible, but they need not be identical.

To be done properly, the paired-field experiment involves two time stages, which can be called the calibration stage and the experiment stage. During the calibration stage, the two fields are observed without any intervention, ideally for a period of 3-5 years, during which the response of interest is measured in each at the same times. This leads to the development of a statistically significant relationship between the response of the two fields. (This relationship is unlikely to be 1:1, because the fields are different, but that does not matter.) Then the experiment is performed on one of the fields, and the second is left unaltered to serve as the control. The result of the experiment is shown by a change in the relationship of the two fields. If we are doing an experiment to see how using winter wheat as a cover crop reduces sediment loss from a field as compared to leaving the field bare, we would expect the slope of the relationship in the experiment phase to be shallower than the slope that was observed in the calibration phase (Figure 1).

The major advantages of this design are that it largely "cancels out" weather effects, and automatically takes account of differences in the properties of the two fields, since the response of interest is a change in the relationship from the first phase to the second, and these properties should remain the same.

Figure 1. Detecting change with the paired-field research design.

Watershed Scale Research

In research at the watershed scale, manipulation is difficult. The researcher does not own the study area, and has to persuade various land owners to cooperate with the experiment. In some situations, the researcher is confined to observing the system and hoping for “natural experiments” such as a large flood that can be interpreted in a useful way. Extraneous influences are abundant and largely uncontrollable. The scale of the research usually prohibits more than one level of treatment, and there may be no *a priori* way to choose the appropriate level of treatment. If there is a control, the researcher is not really in control of it. Replication is rarely economically feasible.

In addition, there may be a long time lag between the time of the experiment and the time when the response is evident. Weather is often the main source of variation in whatever we are measuring, and it constitutes uninteresting “noise” that obscures the “signal” we are trying to detect. The scale of implementation of the experiment may be small, and it may not be possible to target the implementation to the parts of the watershed where it would have the biggest effect. Often, funding agencies are unwilling to fund the calibration phase of the project, making it impossible to be certain that the project has changed anything.

Land management programs face additional problems. Because they are usually implementation-oriented, often little or no monitoring is done to document their effectiveness in improving water quality. The notion of maintaining a control watershed is inconsistent with “solving the problem”. Frequently a watershed has a history of many successive and/or concurrent programs, and if a water quality change is observed, it is unclear which program(s) led to the change. Given the complex variability of water quality data in large watersheds, if a water quality change is not observed, it cannot be inferred that there was none – only that we cannot detect it.

With all of these difficulties, it should not be surprising that watershed-scale research often fails to document water quality responses to land management changes.

Analogy with Laboratory Research

Consider what it might be like to be a laboratory researcher confronted with the same issues that characterize research at the watershed scale. You are a candidate for a Master's degree in chemistry at a university that shall remain nameless. You have been given approval to do the central experiment for your degree and assigned a lab in which to do it. You arrive at the lab and observe a large beaker in the middle of the room, for you to use for your experiment. There is no door in the doorway to the lab and the windows are open. People are going in and out. The wind blows through, bringing dust and leaves with it; some of them are floating around in the beaker. You soon discover that several other students are also doing their research projects in the same beaker. Your reagents are impure – the NaCl is in a round blue Morton's box and the NaHCO₃ is in the familiar yellow Arm & Hammer box. There's no distilled water. And to top it all off, the experiment takes three hours to complete, but you're only allocated 25 minutes!

CASE STUDY: LAKE ERIE CREP

The Lake Erie CREP program is designed to reduce sediment loading to Lake Erie by implementation of buffer strips, riparian corridors, wetlands, and other practices that will reduce erosion within the CREP program area (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Ohio Lake Erie CREP implementation area (bordered by bold line)

Assessment of water quality benefits is based on information from the NCWQR monitoring programs on the Maumee and Sandusky Rivers. The Maumee and Sandusky stations are part of NCWQR's Ohio Tributary Monitoring Program, and

have a more than 25-year record of daily and more frequent sampling for sediment and nutrient conditions. This historical record is the standard against which the success of the Lake Erie CREP will be evaluated.

Establishment of the CREP Sediment Reduction Goal

The water quality goal of the CREP program is to reduce the sediment load from the CREP program area by 15,000 metric tons per year for the first 10 years of the program. This goal was calculated from several other quantities. One is the average load for the Maumee, Sandusky, and Cuyahoga Rivers for the period 1991-1996, 1.5 million metric tons per year, as measured by the NCWQR and reported in the State of Ohio 1998 State of the Lake Report (OLEC, 1998). The other quantity is the primary CREP objective to enroll 10% of the Western Lake Erie Watershed's farmed riparian areas.

The CREP program area (the Western Lake Erie Watershed) does not include the Cuyahoga River basin, but includes several watersheds other than the Maumee and Sandusky. In addition, parts of the Maumee River watershed lie outside of Ohio and therefore outside of the CREP program area. The annual sediment load from the CREP area is unknown. For the purpose of setting a goal, two assumptions were made: 1) The differences in land area between the CREP program area and the Maumee, Sandusky, and Cuyahoga watersheds essentially cancel out, and therefore the 1.5 million metric ton figure from the State of the Lake Report can serve as a reasonable estimate of the loading from the CREP area. 2) The sediment load is derived equally from all parts of the watershed. Neither of these assumptions is likely to be totally true, but they seemed reasonable to establish a goal for sediment loading.

On the basis of these assumptions, it was estimated that installing practices to protect 10% of the riparian areas would lead to 10% reduction in the sediment load, or 150,000 metric tons. Implementation was to be complete after 10 years. A uniform rate of progress was assumed, leading to the goal of 15,000 metric tons per year. The CREP contracts also call for continuation of the practices for 20 years, so it was assumed that after the 10 year implementation period there would follow another 10 year period during which the reduced sediment loading rate would continue without improvement or decline.

Approach to Evaluation

While the goals of the CREP program are stated directly in terms of sediment reductions annually, sediment *reductions* cannot be measured directly. Instead, evaluation of progress must be expressed by comparing the actual sediment loads for the CREP program area with the loads that would be expected under average conditions if no implementation took place as a result of the CREP program. This requires that measured annual loads be extrapolated to the CREP program area as

a whole, and that these be compared with a base load similarly extrapolated. For this purpose, a different analysis is appropriate than the one used to arrive at the objectives listed above.

It is most appropriate to estimate the sediment loads for the CREP program area from the Maumee and Sandusky river loads, excluding the Cuyahoga River loads since the Cuyahoga is not in the program area. To do this, we must :

- estimate the Ohio portion of the Maumee River load by multiplying the observed Maumee load by the proportion of the basin that lies in Ohio upstream from the monitoring station (71.8%)
- add to this the observed Sandusky River load
- extrapolate this observed Maumee + Sandusky load to the entire CREP area by multiplying by the ratio of the total CREP-eligible acres to the area upstream (and in Ohio) of the Maumee and Sandusky monitoring stations (131.7%)

Applying this approach to the historical data (1991-1996) used in the State of the Lake Report leads to an average baseline load for the CREP area of about 1.32 million metric tons per year. This figure is the expected load if no action were taken to improve sediment retention on the land. Compared to this baseline figure, the goal of 150,000 metric tons reduction after 10 years represents an 11.4% reduction, slightly larger than, but close to, the 10% figure used to derive the objective. In addition, it is assumed that no sediment savings will be realized in the first year of the CREP program because of the time lags mentioned above. These assumptions and approaches lead to the sediment savings goals shown in Table 1. These goals will be compared directly with the observed loads (adjusted to the CREP area) over the next 20 years, to evaluate the success of the CREP program in meeting its water quality goals.

Weaknesses of the Lake Erie CREP as Watershed-Scale Research

The Lake Erie CREP project lacks a control watershed – it is a simple before and after comparison. There is a long history of programs related to erosion control and sediment loss reductions in the basin. No one knows what the lag time will be before sediment reductions from this program reach the monitoring station. Consequently it will be difficult to be sure that, if the goal is reached, it is because of the CREP program. Also, if the goal is not reached, it may be because we did not watch long enough.

The 10% implementation goal is not based on any calculation of what is needed to accomplish a specified outcome, rather it amounts to a guess at what it might be possible to achieve. The 10% reduction in sediment loading goal was set without any knowledge of how large a load reduction should accompany 10% implementation. It may be unrealistically large or unrealistically small.

Finally, the targeted reductions amount to 1% per year. This is a rather small change, and quite possibly too small to be detected statistically (Richards and Grabow, 2003).

Table 1. Sediment reduction goals for the Lake Erie CREP

Water Year	Sediment load target	Cumulative sediment load target	Cumulative load, if no action	Estimate of sediment saved
2000	1,320,000	1,320,000	1,320,000	0
2001	1,305,000	2,625,000	2,640,000	15,000
2002	1,290,000	3,915,000	3,960,000	45,000
2003	1,275,000	5,190,000	5,280,000	90,000
2004	1,260,000	6,450,000	6,600,000	150,000
2005	1,245,000	7,695,000	7,920,000	225,000
2006	1,230,000	8,925,000	9,240,000	315,000
2007	1,215,000	10,140,000	10,560,000	420,000
2008	1,200,000	11,340,000	11,880,000	540,000
2009	1,185,000	12,525,000	13,200,000	675,000
2010	1,170,000	13,695,000	14,520,000	825,000
2011	1,170,000	14,865,000	15,840,000	975,000
2012	1,170,000	16,035,000	17,160,000	1,125,000
2013	1,170,000	17,205,000	18,480,000	1,275,000
2014	1,170,000	18,375,000	19,800,000	1,425,000
2015	1,170,000	19,545,000	21,120,000	1,575,000
2016	1,170,000	20,715,000	22,440,000	1,725,000
2017	1,170,000	21,885,000	23,760,000	1,875,000
2018	1,170,000	23,055,000	25,080,000	2,025,000
2019	1,170,000	24,225,000	26,400,000	2,175,000
2020	1,170,000	25,395,000	27,720,000	2,325,000

Evaluation of Success to Date

The adjusted loads for the years for which data are currently available are shown in the table on the next page. It is remarkable to observe that after six years the sediment saved is greater than the target savings after 18 years! However, cumulative discharge for four of the six years of the program also is below average. While the loads are adjusted for differences in discharge, using a simple proportional adjustment, this adjustment may not adequately account for the effects of discharge on the annual load. If this is the case, if we encounter more years with above-average discharge, the reported “savings” may shrink rapidly.

Table 2. Target loads, observed loads, and sediment saved, 2000-2005

Water Year	Cumulative sediment load target	Target sediment saved	Observed sediment load*	Cumulative observed load	Observed sediment saved
2000	1,320,000	0	1,111,027	1,111,027	208,973
2001	2,625,000	15,000	686,190	1,797,217	842,783
2002	3,915,000	45,000	1,119,807	2,917,024	1,042,976
2003	5,190,000	90,000	1,080,912	3,997,936	1,282,064
2004	6,450,000	150,000	840,165	4,838,101	1,761,899
2005	7,695,000	225,000	1,139,654	5,977,755	1,942,245

*Adjusted for differences in discharge between current year and average of water years 1990-1999

On the other hand, it is possible that the BMPs are more successful than expected. Perhaps a 10% implementation level produces a 30% or larger decrease in sediment loads; remember that the 10% target was just a guess.

Finally, sediment concentrations in the Maumee and Sandusky show a distinct downward trend over the last 30 years. The causes of this trend have probably continued to operate while the CREP program has been in place. If so, the CREP programs should not get credit for all of the observed decreases in sediment. However, this longer trend invites a different analysis that will help determine if the trend is due to the mosaic of management programs in these watersheds, or whether it might be due to a spurious factor such as a long-term change in the weather, which would affect sediment concentrations through their relationship to flow.

If this trend is due to the conservation practices that have been applied in these watersheds in the CREP program and its precursors, the relationship between concentration and flow should be changing, with less sediment for a given flow in later years. If this trend is spurious and a consequence of weather and other extraneous influences, we may expect that the concentration-flow relationship has remained essentially unchanged over this time. The Sandusky shows a weak upward trend in flow, and the Maumee shows a very slight increase. These changes in flow should lead to increases in sediment, not the decreases that we have observed.

An analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of log(sediment concentration) as a function of log(flow) and year, where year is treated as a non-numeric categorical variable, provides an estimate of the difference in the concentration-flow relationship for each year from the overall relationship. The analysis shows that there is a highly significant statistical relationship between this difference and the year itself (now treating the year as a continuous numeric variable). This indicates that the concentration-flow relationship has indeed changed substantially over the 30 year period. Both the Maumee and the Sandusky data show this

pattern, and in both cases it is statistically significant, though the relationship is stronger in the Maumee data.

Additional ANCOVAs were performed on data separated into “summer” (May-October) and “winter” (November-April) periods. The downward trend in concentration as a function of flow is seen strongly in the summer data, when most BMPs are most effective, and only weakly in the winter data.

These results strongly suggest that the observed sediment trends are a direct consequence of improvements in land management, and increase the likelihood that the CREP program is indeed leading to decreased loads. Clearly the trends just discussed occurred over a much longer period than that of the CREP project. As CREP implementation continues and data accumulates, it will be interesting to see if we can detect an acceleration of the change in the concentration-flow relationship, which would reflect the additional contribution of the CREP program to the protection of our watersheds from sediment loss.

CONCLUSIONS

For a number of reasons, detecting water quality changes at the watershed scale is difficult, and often requires abundant data gathered over a discouragingly long time. For a number of reasons, making a strong case that detected water quality changes are due to land use changes that were intended to produce them is even more difficult. However, given the right data and appropriate analyses, a fairly strong case for a cause and effect relationship can be made.

In the case of the Ohio Lake Erie CREP program, the conservation practices applied in the program area have led to reductions in sediment loads to Lake Erie compared to those from the 1990's. These reductions are greater and are occurring more quickly than anticipated in the goals set by the program. However, it is unclear how much of the reductions is actually due to the CREP program and how much is due to other past and present programs.

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